

DEVELOPMENT OF A MONITORING AND INVENTORY SYSTEM FOR PROPERTY AND EQUIPMENT USING RAPID APPLICATION DEVELOPMENT (RAD) MODEL

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Development of a Monitoring and Inventory System for Property and Equipment Using Rapid Application Development (RAD) Model

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Abstract

This study was conducted to come up with a program that aims to improve the efficiency of the monitoring and inventory of property and equipment of the Supply and Property Office. Specifically, it aimed to solve problems on system storage data, tracking number for property each equipment, monitoring and updating of the status of incoming and outgoing properties. Generation of reports such as for newly delivered equipment, inventory of property and equipment, for returned equipment, and unserviceable equipment are also given considerations in this study. This system focused only for monitoring and inventory of property and equipment of any offices. The study did not cover the inventory for school supplies or consumable materials as well as the procurement of the equipment and in conducting this study, the researchers used Rapid Application Development (RAD) Model. The researchers conducted an interview and a guide questionnaire to come up with the outline for developing the program that was appropriate to the inventory system of the Supply and Property Office of any of the institutions, offices or organizations. They personally interviewed the in-charge personnel regarding the inventory of property and equipment and other processes. The researchers used different software for their study, Microsoft Visual Basic 2008 as their programming language, Adobe Photoshop for designing of images used on the system and Microsoft Word 2007 for the documentation of the study, all through their laptop. The researchers concluded that the implementation of this proposed system, Monitoring and Inventory System of Property and Equipment would bring the institutions, office or organizations into a potential establishment. The personnel in-charge could easily monitor and update the issued property and equipment and generating accurate reports would be able to experience with them. Finally, it would make their management easy, consistent and reliable.

Keywords: *rapid application development (RAD) model, equipment, process, unserviceable equipment*

Introduction

Proper monitoring of the company in holding stocks is the primary purpose of inventory management. Through proper monitoring, managers can seamlessly determine the incoming and outgoing raw materials. This is usually observed in companies which patronize stocks. This also helps the company to maintain and balance the stocks and for easier evaluation of logistics. It can also monitor the income of the business. It is undeniably the reason for many companies to rely on computerized and inventory systems because it is more convenient, efficient, and requires only minimal manpower to work.

Most of the offices today have a section called Supply and Property Office. The said office is responsible for recording different documents specifically for property and equipment. It is also their responsibility to monitor the whereabouts, determine the status of the properties and equipment and make reports for different transactions.

In monitoring and doing inventory for the property and equipment, the said office usually conducts it every end of the year. Oftentimes, if the office does not have any inventory software, they usually use spreadsheets like Microsoft Excel for encoding the details about the materials and they manually sum it up, save then print. In most cases, this kind of system can be a problem. "With each new set of reports, more spreadsheet files are created and data becomes redundant to encode. Having different files can be a problem in generating a report. One has to search several records, update records, and consolidate data for computation and other processes" (Pilot, 2020). These operations are difficult to do and consume a lot of time.

Hence, this paper proposed for computerization of monitoring and inventory systems for reporting and other processes of properties and equipment. This proposed system will be very suited to the offices which are having difficulties in monitoring and doing inventory for their property and equipment. This study aimed at the concerned people. In the other words, it aimed to make the transaction more efficient, convenient, and productive in a way that the system is capable of generating accurate different reports, updating the status of different equipment, and being capable of tracking the equipment if where is it issued.

Research Questions

This study was conducted to explore the possibility of a program that aims to improve the efficiency of the monitoring and inventory of property and equipment of the Supply and Property Office. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. How would the system provide systematic storage of data?
2. How would the system assign tracking numbers for each equipment property?
3. How would the system monitor and update the status of incoming and outgoing properties and equipment?
4. How would the system generate reports such as for newly delivered equipment, for inventory of property and equipment, for

- returned equipment as well as for unserviceable equipment?
5. How would the system protect the stored from unauthorized users? And
 6. How would the system provide back-up and restoration of files?

Literature Review

Inventory System

This study is anchored to The Jeonsoft Corporation-the company “Jeonsoft Inventory System”. The system equipped different features. This includes unlimited number of users for the system, enumerable numbers of positions or commonly called the access level of the user, unlimited number of clients, user friendly interface, close-monitored data-base, initiates search engine, generates and prints report lists, optional use of unit of conversion, provides accurate computation, and precise control of the stocks (<https://jeonsoft.com/pages/philippine-inventory-system.html>).

The Enterprise One Company is located in Singapore which uses this system, the JD Edwards EnterpriseOne Inventory Management. The system contains features that are essentials to the company that they used in their products. These are the following, first, Item Numbering and Description; the system provided multiple methods of identifying items. The company used actual item numbers, numbers that were designated, or a combination of both. Second is the Stocking Features; typically, a company maintains one or both types of inventory; stock items and non-stock items. Stock items are stored products or parts that are ready for sale. Non-stock items are items that are used by the company, such as office supplies. They used to identify, store, and track stock and non-stock items. Also, they identify and track prices in multiple currencies, identify and store items that require special handling such as refrigeration, identify items that require quality analysis or testing, determine obsolete items and identify and account for broken or defective parts. Third, the Item Locations; the JD Edwards EnterpriseOne Inventory Management system helped them to create locations and track the items through a vast number of item locations (http://docs.oracle.com/cd/E16582_01/doc.91/e15119/get_strtd_with_inv_mgmnt.htm).

Equipment/Tool Organizer Pro (School Equipment Inventory is a universal system used specifically for inventory of school supplies and equipment. This system is used by many organizations that have their own school supplies and equipment such as schools and a store. The system can easily manage the school inventories and it tracks equipment users. It processes check in and out transactions, loan management, and lists overdue items. Create school equipment circulation reports, inventory report prints barcode labels, borrower ID cards, give access to equipment inventories, search module, protect databases, process backup, store other important data, and repair transactions, and suppliers (http://www.primasoft.com/pro_software/school_equipment_inventory_software.htm).

After implementing those features, the company of each system provided an easier and faster way to monitor the movement of their business’ stock of goods; from transferring of goods from one warehouse to another, item entry, releasing of items, inventory adjustment, and production. It was also their way of providing good quality of inventory through accurate reports of their different processes. It made them more productive in a way that all of their transactions can be done in a short span of time. They also secured their data stored.

The above-mentioned related systems equipped with different features that were essential for inventory processes. This proposed system adapted some of those features are; the unlimited user of the system, and user friendly interface for the user to be easily used the features of the system, tracking of incoming and outgoing equipment and school supplies, generating different reports, searching of records, identifying the condition of the equipment and school supplies, and protecting the database.

The proposed system did not include identifying the price of the items in multiple currencies. The use of a barcode scanner which provides faster processing of transactions is also excluded in this proposed system, RFID and any special devices that could be used for inventory purposes. The proposed system was also not capable of any online transactions.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative research method and utilized an interview guide questionnaire. The participants were subjected to interviews and demonstrations of their respective work assignments. Thematic analysis was used to interpret their answers to each question.

Respondents

The primary respondents of the study are twenty-eight (28) personnel in-charge of some offices of Mindanao State University – Maguindanao. These personnel are of legal ages, well trained in their field, and are serving the institution for at least a year. The respondents were subjected to interview questions.

Instrument

The researchers employed interview guide questions. This interview guide questionnaire was validated by four language teachers and five Information Technology professors. Using Likert scale in the validation process, the interview guide questionnaire garnered a

general average of 4.13 which is described as valid.

After the validation process, the researcher came up with the outline for developing the program that was appropriate to the inventory system of the Supply and Property Office of any of the institutions, offices or organizations. The interview consisted of questions which indicated their inventory reporting and management system. The researcher personally interviewed the in-charge personnel regarding the inventory of property and equipment and other processes. The researchers used different software for their study, Microsoft Visual Basic 2008 as their programming language, Adobe Photoshop for designing of images used on the system and Microsoft Word 2007 for the documentation of the study, all through their laptop.

Procedure

Development Model

In conducting this study, the researchers used the Rapid Application Development (RAD) Model. This methodology was appropriate in developing the Computerized Monitoring and Inventory System. It was also the fastest way to meet the objectives of the study in a way that the RAD model techniques were clear and understandable in the development of the software as the researchers involved user and management participation in reviewing and testing the software. Any development added, errors, or omissions on this system were properly coded for proper monitoring of the quality of the system and to reduce the possible risks.

Development Approach

Before the researchers conducted this study, they first identified what system they were going to develop. They realized that the Monitoring and Inventory System of Property and Equipment would be their system to be proposed in a way that it was suitable to their capability and any office could use it. Since the researchers did not have a respondent, they searched for organization or establishment in or near in their school which has Supply and Property Office and luckily their institution, Mindanao State University-Maguindanao allowed them to ask any information regarding their property and equipment. They asked about what transactions or reports they usually do for the said materials. The researchers made a guide questionnaire and oral interview. The personnel in-charge of the office did not refuse to answer the questions, and with the help of the guide questionnaire, the researchers clearly understood the flow of the transactions of the office. After the interview was done, the personnel in-charge gave sample reports to the researchers they made use of it.

Schedule and Timeline

The figure below shows the schedules activities of the researchers in developing this study.

Legend:
 Finished: ■ Unfinished: □

Ethical Considerations

The researcher adheres to the highest possible ethical considerations and standards in conducting the study through seeking formal approval from the institution by writing. The letter explains the purpose, methods, and expected outcomes of the study, as well as the

potential benefits and risks for the participants. The researchers also made sure to obtain informed consent from the participants, explaining the nature of the study, their rights, and their privacy.

Additionally, the researchers made sure that every piece of information gathered for this study was handled with the highest security and privacy. This includes storing data in secure locations with restricted access and identifying participants using anonymous codes rather than personal information. The researcher also comited to permanently delete the data at the end of the study as a way of taking precautions against illegal access, disclosure, or use of the data. The researcher was able to carry out the study responsibly and with respect by adhering to these ethical standards and procedures, safeguarding the rights and well-being of the participants as well as the validity and reliability of the study's conclusions.

Results and Discussion

This presents the result of the study, and the development of the system as a whole.

Program Hierarchy

The figure above shows the system hierarchy of the proposed system. It shows the sequential process of the system. It would help the user to familiarize the different modules and the flow of the system.

Figure 1.1. Log in Form

Figure 1.1 is a Log-in Form. This form provides systematic security to the system. It allows the user to access the system depending on what access level he is authorized to access. This form contains textboxes and buttons. The user is required to enter his username and password to access the system. If the username does not match the saved username on the database, the system will not allow the user to access the system. If the username and the password match the registered account, the form brings the user in the main menu where he can modify the features of the system upon clicking the “OK” button. If the user wants to cancel the process, the form closes by clicking the “Close” button.

Figure 1.2. Main Menu Form

Figure 1.2 is the Main Menu Form. This form allows the user to access all the features of the system if he is in the admin level. The user can perform all the systematic transactions equipped on this system. The form contains the text field above that the user can select what module he wants to access. Now, he can perform the data entries, generating necessary reports and other processes of the system such as for searching and updating different records.

Figure 1.3. Add Category Form

Figure 1.3 is the Add Category Form. The user can input the category name on the textbox and its identification will systematically generate and it will save by clicking the “Save” button. By clicking “Close” button, the form will close.

Figure 1.4. Create Account Form

Figure 1.4 is the Create Account Form. This form allows the user to add another user of the system. This form can be accessed only by admin level. It allows the admin user to create an account for another user who will use the system. After the required information is

input, the current user must select the access level. If the current user will select the “Admin”, the other user can access all the features of the system while the other one, the “User”, limited features can access the user. For clicking the “Sign Up” button, all encoded information will save on the database. “Cancel” button will close the form upon clicking of it.

Figure 1.5. Add Employee Form

Figure 1.5 is the Add Employee Form. This form allows the user to store an employee’s information who will receive a property or equipment. When the user encodes the information needed on the “textboxes”, by clicking the “Add” button, automatically the information will be saved. Upon clicking the “Close” button, the form will be closed.

Name	Position	Office
Engr. Marcial C. Arcega	Chairman	College of Arts and Sciences
Prof. Lenie L. Fontanilla	Professor I	College of Arts and Sciences
Prof. Ryl R. Ramos	Professor I	College of Arts and Sciences
Sandra F. Dumacil	Instructor I	College of Arts and Sciences

Figure 1.6. Employee Set Up Form

Figure 1.6 Employee Set Up Form. It is for viewing purposes. It allows the user to see who are the employees that are registered on the database.

Category	Name	Description	Unit Value	Quantity
IT EQUIPMENT	Computer	Win8, Asus	123456.00	4
SCIENTIFIC EQUIPME...	Microscope	qwerty	1000.00	5
IT EQUIPMENT	Cpu	vdcsd	2322.00	22

Figure 1.7. Add New Equipment Form

Figure 1.7 is the Add New Equipment Form. The use of this form is for adding new equipment only. This form provides systematic storing of equipment’s information. The information requires to input on the “textboxes”. When the user will click the “Add” button, the information will automatically save and it will show on the “table”.

Figure 1.8. Issuance of Equipment Form

Figure 1.8 is Issuance of Equipment Form. The user must search the employee by selecting the “Name” or the “ID Number” of the employee by clicking the “radiobuttons”. After selecting, the user must enter the name or the ID number of the employee to find his information. By clicking the “Search” button, it will automatically display the information of the employee on the “textboxes”. The form contains “2 tables”. The first table shows all available equipment. All which equipment belong to the specific category will appear on the table after selecting the equipment category by pressing the “Combo Box”. “Refresh” button will refresh the content of the table. The user must point the cursor on the table and press the “Right Click” then the “Add” button will show. By clicking the add button, the figure 1.8 will show. The selected equipment will save on the other table. The “Print” button allows the user to preview the report of the transaction. The form will close by clicking the “Close” button.

Figure 1.9. Enter Quantity Form

Figure 1.9 is the Enter Quantity Form. This form allows the user to enter the quantity of the equipment to be issued on the employee. By clicking the “OK” button, the quantity will save and continue the transaction.

Figure 2. Add Property Form

Figure 2 is the Add Property Form. This form allows the user to add new property. The purpose of this form is for storing property information. The information will automatically save on the database by clicking the “Add” button after the required information is encoded on the “textboxes”. By clicking the “Close” button, the form will close.

Property Number	Category	Property Name	Description	Unit Value
prop-127	Building	IT Building	IT Building	1,789,897.78
prop-128	Land	MSU Campus	6 Hectares	78,347,356.56

Figure 2.1. Issuance of Property Form

Figure 2.1 is the Issuance of Property Form. This form is tasked for issuance of property only. The form contains “Tables”, “Print”, and “Close” button. The concept of searching for the employee’s information is the same with Figure 2.0. The user must input the employee’s identification on the textbox and must click the “Search” button to display the information. The user can only issue the property by selecting the property and by pressing the “Enter” on the computer keyboard. After the issuance is done, the user can produce the report by clicking the “Print” button. The user can close the form by clicking the “Close” button.

Category	Equipment Name	Description	Unit Value	Quantity	Total Value	Date Purchased
IT EQUIPMENT	Computer	Win8. Aus	123456.00	4	453824.00	11/16/2014
SCIENTIFIC EQUIPMENT	Microscope	querty	1000.00	5	5000.00	11/12/2014
IT EQUIPMENT	Cou	vbcd	2322.00	22	51084.00	12/24/2014

Figure 2.2. View Equipment Form

Figure 2.2 is the View Equipment Form. This figure shows all available equipment and it displays also the equipment’s information. The user will see the unissued equipment through this form. The form contains “Combo Box” and “Refresh” button. By selecting category type, the equipment which belong to specific category will appear. By clicking the refresh button, the table will refresh.

EQUIPMENTCODE	Category	NAME	Description	UNITVALUE	WABOUT	CONDITION	DATEISSUED
IT1001-2	IT EQUIPMENT	Computer	Win8. Aus	123456	Sandra F. Dumacil	Good Condition	11/20/2014 3:54:45

Figure 2.3. Search Issued Equipment Form

Figure 2.3 is the Search Issued Equipment Form. This form consists of “Search”, “Refresh”, “Close”, “Radio Button”, and “Table”. This figure is for searching purposes. It allows the user to view the equipment’s information. The user must select the identification to use for searching. The information will display on the table by clicking the search table after entering the identification on the textbox. Refresh button is used to refresh the table and close button to close the form.

EQUIPMENTCODE	Category	NAME	Description	UNITVALUE	WABOUT	CONDITION	DATEISSUED
IT1001-2	IT EQUIPMENT	Computer	Win8 Asus	123456	Sandra F. Dumacil	Good Condition	11/20/2014 3:54:45 PM

Figure 2.4. Update Issued Equipment's Information Form

Figure 2.4 is the Update Record Form. This form provides systematic updating of the condition of the equipment. The form contains “Textboxes”, “Radio Buttons”, “Search”, “Refresh”, and “Close” buttons. For searching the equipment, the user must select first what type of identification he wants to use. Tracking Number” of specific equipment shows itself automatically on the system alone, the “Receiver” displays all the equipment issued to the specific equipment’s receiver while the “Equipment Name” will show only that equipment belong to the specific equipment name. The selected identification must enter on the first textbox and click the search button to show the equipment’s information. After the equipment is found, the condition of the equipment will display on the second textbox that the user can update. By clicking the update button, the condition will be automatically updated. Refresh button will refresh the table and the close button will close the form.

EQUIPMENT CODE	CATEGORY	NAME	DESCRIPTION	UNIT VALUE	ISSUED TO	CONDITION	DATE ISSUE
SC1304-8	SCIENTIFIC EQUIP	Microscope	olympus	1,000.00	Sandra F. Dumacil	Good Condition	1/4/2014 9:40
PE1000-1	FURNITURES AND IT	Chair	xxxxxx	100.00	Frayz Mumental C. Aranga	Good Condition	11/15/2014
IT1001-2	ITEQUIPMENT	Computer	Win8 Asus	12,345.65	Sandra F. Dumacil	Damaged	11/20/2014
Qty: 3				Total:	13,445.65		

Figure 2.5. Print All Report Form

Figure 2.5 is the Print All Report Form. This form is equipment’s master list where the user can preview and print all the issued equipment with the different employees. Furthermore, the user can use the time range for printing the equipment’s information that will base on the time when the equipment are issued, by entering the starting date at the first text field and the end date on the second one. By clicking the “Preview” button, the selected equipment will appear.

EQUIPMENT CODE	CATEGORY	NAME	DESCRIPTION	UNIT VALUE	CONDITION	DATE ISS
IT1001-3	ITEQUIPMENT	Keyboard	Standard keyboard	150.00	Good Condition	1/4/2015
PE1000-0	FURNITURES AND IT	Sub	xxxxxx	100.00	Good Condition	11/17/20
IT1001-2	ITEQUIPMENT	Computer	Win8 Asus	12,345.65	Good Condition	11/20/20
Qty: 3				Total:	12,595.97	

Figure 2.6. Individual Report Form

Figure 2.6 is the Individual Report Form. This figure shows the individual report for the issuance of the equipment. Before the report appears, the name of the employee must be searched. By entering the employee name and by clicking the “Preview” button. This form also contains radio buttons that allow the user to select the mode of report printing, either printing all issued or by selecting the time range. By selecting “All”, all issued equipment belong to a specific employee, by clicking the “Preview” button, automatically it shows, and if the user will select the “By date range,” he must enter the date range to preview the desired report.

Figure 2.7. By Category Report Form

Figure 2.7 is the By Category Report Form. This form prints only the issued equipment belong to their own category. This also figure contains text field that enables the user to enter the category name of the issued equipment. By clicking the “Preview” button, the equipment which belong to the specific category appear. This form also contains two modes of report printing. By “All” and “By date range”.

Figure 2.8. Newly Issued Equipment Report Form

Figure 2.8 is the Newly Issued Equipment Report Form. This form will only show after the issuance of the equipment is done. This form prints only the newly issued equipment.

Figure 2.9. Unserviceable Equipment Report Form

Figure 2.9 is the Unserviceable Equipment Report Form. This form shows only all the unserviceable equipment issued to any employee. For selecting “All”, all unserviceable equipment will be printed but if the user enters the date range, the equipment cover only of the entered dates will show, all through by clicking the “Preview” button.

Figure 3. *New Property Report Form*

Figure 3 is the New Property Report Form. This form provides report for new property. Upon searching the date through clicking the “Search” button, the information will automatically show.

Figure 3.1. *Update Account Form*

Figure 3.1 is the Update Account Form. This form is intended for updating a user account only. The figure contains searching for the user account by entering the name on the textbox and by clicking the “Search” button. When the account is found, it can be updated by entering the old password and change it into new one. When the user clicks the “Cancel” button, the button will close.

Figure 3.2. *Back Up File Form*

Figure 3.2 is the Back Up File Form. This form shows how the system enabled the user to back-up the files from the current directory of the data or records to a folder destination from any other directory or drive of the computer.

Figure 3.3 is the Restore File Form. This form allows the user to restore the files from the back up files’ directory of the data or records to the current directory.

Figure 3.3. Restore File Form

Monitoring and Inventory System was developed in order to have an accurate inventory and monitoring of property and equipment of any of institutions, offices and organizations that has a Supply and Property Office. This proposed system serves as their way to make their establishment more productive in a way that the system is capable of tracking the issued equipment. In that way, there would be no losing of equipment anymore. Furthermore, the system is also capable of generating different reports such as inventory reports, returned equipment from the employee, newly purchased equipment of the institutions, offices and organizations and unserviceable equipment. It also includes updating the status or the condition of the equipment.

Conclusions

The implementation of this proposed system, Monitoring and Inventory System of Property and Equipment would bring the institutions, office or organizations into a potential establishment. They would greatly improve their task in terms of monitoring their properties and equipment. It would also provide them a better inventory and monitoring processes. The personnel in-charge could easily monitor and update the issued property and equipment and generating accurate reports would be able to experience with them. Finally, it would make their management easy, consistent and reliable.

The researchers recommended that this proposed system should be implemented for those institutions, offices or organizations that are lack of computerized system. This proposed system can used for monitoring and inventory purposes. This system would also be needed to monitor their facilities for them to trace the location of issued property and equipment, and also the availability of those materials. Moreover, it is also recommended that aside from monitoring and inventory, other processes should be implemented for better management. Using special devices such as barcode scanner is also recommended to make the issuance of equipment become faster. In order to be knowledgeable in using the system, the user of this system must undergo seminar about how to use the features of the system. Maintenance of the system and backing up of files must be done also for the system to last longer.

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